

REDUCTION OF MOBILE FORMS OF HEAVY METALS USING MICROORGANISM STRAINS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13883613>

Abstract. This article focuses on reducing the content of heavy metals in typical and meadow gray soils that were artificially contaminated with Cr, Ni, Cd, Pb, and Cu at concentrations 3, 5, and 10 times higher than the maximum permissible concentration (MPC). Positive results were observed with strains of microorganisms, including *Bacillus atropeus* (No. 4), *Enterobacter cloacae* (No. 5), *Enterobacter ludwigii* (No. 11), and *Bacillus cereus* (No. 14).

Keywords: microorganism strains, heavy metals, soil.

Introduction. Nowadays the amount of toxic heavy metals in the soil is increasing. With the increase in the amount of heavy metals, the negative impact on crop plants is primarily due to the agrochemical state of the soil along with various changes. Along with its negative consequences, there was a shift in the trophic chain. The trophic chain includes soil-water-heavy metals-plants and causes various diseases for human health under the influence of toxicants.

Literature review. In stress situations caused by heavy metals, microorganisms either die from metal toxicity or develop metal resistance mechanisms [11], while fungal and bacterial isolates are resistant to heavy metals such as copper, lead and chromium, which shows that it is possible lead to metal biosorption. It is resistant to many heavy metals such as copper, zinc, iron, nickel, lead and cadmium [5], and similar studies have been conducted by scientists [6, 7, 9, 14, 16].

Biofilms produced by microbes are composed of extracellular polymers that can accumulate metal ions and therefore protect the cells within them [20].

Copper ions in soil are highly toxic to microorganisms when present in excessive concentrations [4], leading to changes in the biological balance of the soil, which negatively affects soil fertility, plant development and crop yields [10].

Copper has been used extensively in industry and agriculture since the mid-18th century and is now accumulating in soil. As copper concentrations increase, it negatively affects bacterial abundance and evenness. Our analysis revealed the existence of six functional response groups, each consisting of bacterial taxa with copper-like tolerance responses [17].

In Chashka Petri experiments, changes in element abundance were observed upon inoculation of different microbial strains with 3-, 5- and 10-fold element contamination. The strains of microorganisms *Bacillus atropeus* (No. 4), *Enterobacter cloacae* (No. 5), *Enterobacter ludwigii* (No. 11) and *Bacillus cereus* (No. 14) were used.

According to the results of the first study, it was noted that an average of 1742 mg of copper ions were found in one kg of soil, and the activity of copper ions increased with the activity of moisture and strains and the death of microorganism cells over 5 months in the control variant 5331 mg / kg, in each of the variants using microorganism strains, the following indicators were determined. Copper ions are 5.603 mg / kg in the case of *Bacillus atrofeus* (No. 4), *Enterobacter cloacal* (No. 5) - 5.45 mg / kg, *Enterobacter ludwigii* (No. 11) - 5.25 mg / kg, *Bacillus cereus* (No. 11). 14) – 5.019 mg/kg of copper ions were determined.

CuSO₄ 10 REM *Enterobacter cloacal* (No. 5) in the soils of the 14 most active variants showed a decrease of 6339 mg/kg compared to the control in May, when a 10-fold contaminated variant was observed. Instead of 19.415 mg/kg with 5-fold copper contamination, 15.68 mg/kg remained (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Effect of microorganism strains on copper ion change, mg/kg

It can be concluded that in all variants contaminated with chromium, the situation shown in the graph does not lead to ion recovery. On the contrary, this means that we can see positive results in variants if the permissible amount (REM) for soil of mobile chromium is 6 mg/kg.

In the control and all variants, the amount of ions per kg of soil during the first inspection was low, and in May inspections, on the contrary, an increase in the amount of ions was observed (Fig. 2).

Although variants 13-16 were contaminated with chromium ions 10 times, a decrease in metal ions was observed by 14,548 mg/kg in the *Bacillus atrofeus* strain (No. 7), and in the biopreparation prepared from the *Bacillus atrofeus* strain (No. 7), by 20,305 mg/kg. *Enterobacter ludwigii* (No. 11). Such a situation was observed in variant 5 with an increase in chromium contamination by 3 times, a decrease in the element ion by 1.615 mg/kg, and in variant 6 by 9.359 mg/kg. This condition was reduced to 1342 mg/kg in *Enterobacter ludwigii* strain (No.11) in 5-fold contaminated soil variants, demonstrating a 100% reduction compared to REM (Fig. 2).

Positive results are achieved when using biopreparations based on *Enterobacter ludwigii* strains (11) in cleaning soil from contamination with chromium ions.

The permissible amount of cobalt in the soil is 5 mg/kg, while 20 g of soil in a Petri dish are contaminated 3-5-10 times, reducing the mobile forms of the element with microorganisms.

Acinobacter lwoffi (No. 1), Bacillus pumilis (Bacillus licheniformis (No. 10) and Enterobacter ludwigii (No. 11) strains were used, positive results can be seen on the graph.

Figure 2. Depletion of the element in variant soils contaminated with chromium ions, mg/kg

Each of the strains isolated by the cobalt ion had a high preference for restoring the mobile form of the ion, and in 15 variants with 10-fold contamination with cobalt, the mobile form of the elements in March in 1 kg of soil - 2364 mg/kg, and in May - 5080 mg/kg. The element ion turned out to be less than REE in variants 7 and 11 with 3- and 5-fold contamination of the soil, i.e. 1694 and 1504 mg/kg (Fig. 3).

All analyses showed that there were fewer REE elements, but in the analyses conducted in May, in all variants except variant 12, higher quantities were detected than in March. Variant 12 revealed ionic residues of 1.677 mg/kg, while in March this figure was 8.156 mg/kg (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Depletion of the element in variant soils contaminated with cobalt ion, mg/kg

It was found that 55-45% of microorganism strains reduce the mobility of heavy metals (Fig. 3).

In conclusion, it can be said that the sorption of ions by microorganisms is due to the fact that, when they die, they envelop the ion with a chitinous coating. This is due to the fact that the mobility of the element decreases. Microorganisms, which are considered sorbents, reduce their mobility by enveloping ions with a chitinous layer.

REE zinc in mobile form in the soil is 23 mg/kg, and in strains of *Enterobacter cloacal* (No. 5), *Enterobacter ludwigii* (No. 11), *Bacillus cereus* (No. 14) and *Bacillus pumilis* (No. 24). The indicator is observed in variant 13. The element, exceeding the REE by 12 times, in May observations was 226,599 mg/kg, which remained 9.85 times higher than the REE.

The strain *Bacillus pumilis* (No. 24) did not reduce the amount of lead ions in the 10-fold contaminated variant of REE. This situation was also observed in variants 5 and 9. Because the content of the element decreased by 0.75 times when it was contaminated by 3 times higher than the REE and by 1.32 times when it was contaminated by 5 times higher than the REE (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Depletion of the element in variant soils contaminated with zinc ion, mg/kg

In the studies of S.A. Peshkov and others, using X-ray fluorescence analysis and atomic force microscopy, it was shown that bacteria belonging to the *Bacillus* species accumulate metals. The *B. flicheniformis* 7038 strain was considered the most resistant to high concentrations of metals among all the studied bacteria. However, the localization of metal accumulation has not been fully established. In the case of lead, one can only conclude that it is largely adsorbed on the surface of cells, but this does not exclude the accumulation of lead inside, it is mentioned that other studies will be conducted [1].

The mobile form of lead in the soil is 6 mg / kg REE, and in the studies conducted in March, microorganisms *Bacillus atropheus* (No. 4), *Enterobacter cloacal* (No. 5), *Enterobacter ludwigii* (No. 11) and *Bacillus cereus* (No. 14) strains, their ability to withstand 3-5-10-fold pollution with elements in the soil composition and their superiority are determined (Fig. 5).

In the control soils, the lead content exceeded the REE by 1.5 times, and in the contaminated soils, an excess of the element of the established standards was noted (by 3-5 and 10 times). In the control variants, 8.22, 7.71, 7.58 and 7.50 mg / kg were detected, which is 1.37-1.28-1.26-1.25 times more than in BDM. Thus, 2 months after inoculation of the strains into

contaminated Perti dishes, the analysis of metal ions in the soil was observed at a level of 2.85-3.01-2.69-2.99 mg/kg in the control variants. The increase in the number of ions is caused by the death of microorganisms and the rapid disintegration of the chitinous shell, which leads to the transition of the sorbed ions back into a mobile form (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Reduction of the element in variant soils contaminated with lead ions, mg/kg.

The content in the soil decreased from 20.83 mg/kg to 9.21 mg/kg when adding the *Bacillus atropeus* strain (No. 4) to the 3-fold contaminated variant with lead REE, and to the *Bacillus cereus* strain (No. 14). In the five-fold contaminated variant, a decrease was observed from 15.67 mg per kilogram of soil to 7.27 mg in May. The highest indicator was 10-fold contamination of the soil with REE, the nature of their movement was the following descending series of strains: *Bacillus atropeus* (No. 4) → *Enterobacter cloacal* (No. 5) → *Enterobacter ludwigii* (No. 11) → *Bacillus cereus* (No. 5). 14) (Picture 5).

In conclusion, it should be noted that the positive results were obtained in the transfer of heavy metal ions of microorganisms from one species to another or in the rupture of their ionic bonds, reducing the mobility of toxic elements.

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